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Affect, Precarity, Unhousing: Reading Trends in Twenty-first-century US Literature

Dolores Resano (Universidad Complutense de Madrid)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3328-5199>

Abstract:

In the last two decades, discussions of ‘precarity,’ ‘precariousness,’ and ‘precarisation’ have taken up a prominent space in critical and cultural discussions, especially in Euro-American scholarship, a prominence that is also reflected in the literary arena with the articulation of a cohesive body of works that has been designated ‘the literature of precarity’ or the ‘precarity novel’. There is, however, a significant gap in US literary fiction, one that this article argues is beginning to shift in recent years. After a consideration of what is implied by ‘precarity’ in contemporary discourse and how it translates into a distinct aesthetics of ‘precarious realism’—in particular, how the notion of ‘unhousing’ as physical displacement and affective divestment is pivotal to delineating its ideological permutations—the essay illustrates how the turn to precarity may be taking shape in recent US literature. It does so by considering, first, two novels usually associated with the US ‘novels of the crisis’ that emerged out of the 2007-2008 financial collapse, then turning its attention to Lynn Steger Strong’s *Want* (2020), a novel that is a clear departure from the former category and which can rightly be argued as a novel of precarity.

Keywords: affect, cruel pessimism, unhousing, precarity novel, precarious realism, twenty-first-century US fiction

In their seminal *Cruel Optimism* Lauren Berlant offered the notions of ‘crisis ordinariness’ and ‘cruel optimism’ as useful tools with which to read the first decade of the twenty-first century—a decade saturated with discourses of crisis, permanent war, privatisation, the extension of precarity after the 2008 financial collapse and the resulting housing crisis, but which was, at the same time, infused with the optimism brought about by the election of Barack Obama to

the US Presidency.¹ A decade later, and despite any measures taken to address the worst effects of the so-called Great Recession, some of the fantasies that Berlant had identified as ‘fraying’ may have been already and irretrievably lost. The present seems effectively mired in the permanent crisis of neoliberalism (or what Nancy Fraser has aptly called ‘cannibal capitalism’), endemic socioeconomic uncertainty, climate emergency, and the rapid decline of long-standing liberal values across Western democracies under the sway of far-right populist politics.² This has led some critics (like Berlant herself and, more recently, Robyn Wiegman) to argue for an atmospheric, tonal shift, sensing a disturbance that calls into question whether the optimistic drive (even if cruel) is still available at all. The mood has shifted toward a sense of living in a kind of ‘terminal present’, a ‘desire for all things to end’, which Wiegman associates with a feeling of ‘cruel pessimism’, borrowing from Dia Da Costa’s original formulation in a different context.³ Cruel pessimism is, according to Da Costa, that which ‘feels virtually (im)possible’,⁴ and while it still retains a mutually constitutive relation with sentimental optimism—that ‘scene of negotiated sustenance that makes life bearable’⁵ described in Berlant’s *Cruel Optimism*—this foregrounding helps Wiegman to examine pessimism as one of the dominant affects in the United States of the twenty-first century, where the radicalization of politics and institutions under the effects of Trumpism is compounded by a socioeconomic context of ongoing endemic precarisation.⁶

In what follows, I examine how this tonal shift from optimism to pessimism can also be sensed in much of twenty-first-century literature and, in particular, in the body of works that is usually referred to as ‘the literature of precarity’ or the ‘precarity novel’, as Liam Connell has recently framed it.⁷ My point of departure is that while a ‘turn to precarity’ has been convincingly argued in various disciplines and fields of cultural representation in the United States, it has not yet been, to my knowledge, fully examined in US literary fiction. My aim in this essay is to demonstrate how this turn to precarity—otherwise clearly identified in various European literatures since at least the 1990s—is already visible in recent US fiction, and also how the notion of ‘unhousing’ may be pivotal to thinking about its attendant aesthetics.

After a consideration of what is implied by ‘precarity’ in contemporary scholarship, my analysis seeks to illustrate how this turn may be taking shape in US literature by considering, first, two novels usually associated with an earlier corpus—the US ‘novels of the crisis’ that emerged out of the 2007-2008 financial collapse and its aftermath—and then turning my attention to Lynn Steger Strong’s *Want* (2020), a novel that, I argue, is a departure from the former category and can rightly be argued as a novel of precarity in the terms defined by Connell.⁸ I will suggest that while all three novels can be said to revolve around a sense of

‘crisis’, their ideological investments and aesthetics are qualitatively different, and that this distinction hinges, to a large extent, on shifting expectations and attitudes in matters of housing. Indeed, and as Connell suggests, questions of housing (or lack thereof) are central to the literature of precarity,⁹ and I will rely here on the notion of ‘unhousing’ not just in its literal sense—as the experience of displacement, vulnerability, and exposure—but also as a fraying of expectations, a sort of pessimistic gesture that is central to the experience of precarity in the present. Therefore, my analysis traces the movement from a desire for homeownership that is still available (even if cruel or ill-advised) in two paradigmatic novels of the crisis—Adam Haslett’s *Union Atlantic* (2010) and Jess Walter’s *The Financial Lives of the Poets* (2009)—to a sort of flat affect in Strong’s *Want*, where the shift from homeownership to tenancy has already taken place. In the former works, we can still perceive those ‘technologies of patience’—optimistic neoliberal buzzwords like ambition, responsibility, self-actualization, autonomy—that in *Want* have given way to a pervasive sense of stasis and the negation of any reason for optimistic relief, with the narrator displaced from one precarious tenancy to another.¹⁰ In short, I want to consider how the representation of an encroaching sense of precariousness and pessimism in contemporary US fiction can also be articulated as a form of unhousing, understood here as both physical displacement and affective divestment.

Precarity and the novel

In the last two decades, discussions of ‘precarity’, ‘precariousness’, and ‘precarisation’ have taken up a prominent space in critical and cultural discussions, especially in Euro-American discourse and scholarship.¹¹ As noted, this prominence is also reflected in the literary arena with the articulation of a cohesive body of works that Connell designates the ‘precarity novel’,¹² a corpus usually associated with the emergence of that new social class that Guy Standing identified in 2011 as ‘the precariat’¹³—even though scholars like Maribel Casas-Cortés remind us that ‘the precariat had already named itself’¹⁴ a decade before Standing’s seminal work in grassroots, activist organizations in southern Europe. In general terms, studies concerned with the conceptual field of precarity tend to distinguish between precarity as a socioeconomic concept (with labour precarity being one of the main points of discussion, together with the retreat of the ‘social’ in post-45 social democracies) and ontological precariousness in the terms described by Judith Butler; that is, as an inherent human condition of vulnerability and interdependence.¹⁵ This simple distinction does not, however, reflect the wide variety of interests and disciplinary uses of this cluster of terms, which range from Pierre

Bourdieu's theorization of precarity as the defining condition of advanced capitalist societies, to Guy Standing's conceptualization of 'the precariat' as a new social class that emerges out of deteriorated work conditions and lack of access to social benefits, through Ben Anderson's exploration of precarity as a structure of feeling, Javier López Alós's study of the relationship between precariousness and intellectual life, to Judith Butler's reflections on the ethical implications of precariousness and vulnerability as conditions inherent to social beings, and Isabell Lorey's work on precarisation as a Foucauldian means of governmentality in the neoliberal present, to name but a few.¹⁶ In short, precarity is a term that implies both political economy and biopolitical subjectivity because it refers not just to 'the uncertainty of labor, but also to the insecurity of life, civic identity, and physical and emotional well-being'.¹⁷

Beyond the histories and wide range of theoretical uses of the conceptual field of 'precarity', many have questioned the usefulness of this sustained focus by Euro-American cultural criticism as a term with which to explore a purportedly 'new' social condition of insecurity and uncertainty produced by neoliberalism, especially since precariousness is definitely not a new condition: What does seem to be new, however, is its extension to a formerly 'secure' cohort of people. As Emily Hogg argues in her introduction to *Precarity in Contemporary Literature and Culture*, the critical focus on the term perhaps only points to the fact that it 'may only seem like a distinctively contemporary phenomenon for those of the Global North'.¹⁸ Indeed, and as Albena Azmanova points out, the term 'precarity' appears for the first time in English language dictionaries in 2017 and 2018, 'a sign that the existing concept, precariousness, is somehow deficient in conveying the nature of the vulnerability that has beset societies', which she defines as a 'novel social pathology'.¹⁹ In this sense, I will not be claiming that the experience of precariousness is a novel condition, but I will suggest that the sustained critical attention on the various forms that precarity takes in affluent Western societies is not only saying something about the present but translates into distinct aesthetic and affective forms that are worth exploring. There is, in other words, a specificity to this 'feeling precarious' in the twenty-first century,²⁰ an experience of precariousness that is distinct from other considerations and cultural representations of structural poverty, class inequality, or existential precariousness on the basis of race, ethnicity, gender, or nationality. In fact, one of the first questions that comes to mind when thinking about the literature of precarity as a distinct genre is how it is in any way different from earlier working-class fictions or proletarian literatures. As I will argue in upcoming sections, it is precisely the absence of class-consciousness or its intrinsic class incoherence that keeps the poetics of precarity diffuse, yet easily recognizable.

It is worth noting also that while US scholarship has engaged critically with the contours of precarity as a twenty-first-century condition (most notably, the work of Lauren Berlant), there is a dearth of critical engagement in its relation to US literary fiction, and one can only speculate whether this has to do with its emergent status or with terminological preferences when dealing with a concept that so challenges the ideological foundations of the ‘American Dream’. In fact, this critical gap is quite remarkable when considering that there is already a cohesive and coherent corpus of precarity novels in different European literatures that speak to a shared experience of precarity in the West.²¹ Just as neoliberal globalization has rendered national boundaries porous (at least in our imaginaries, for they in reality remain stubbornly closed for some) and done much to homogenize our tastes and experiences of the present—none more visible than in the gentrified city centres of major tourist destinations—one is left to wonder about the novel of precarity in US fiction. Especially because the experience of twenty-first-century precarity is by no means foreign to the United States; in fact, it has been well argued and examined in other areas of US cultural production, such as US film, British-American televisual media, US culture at large and, incipiently, for US drama.²² In what follows, then, I want to consider whether, and if so, how, we can identify a trend in recent US literary fiction towards a poetics of precarity, one that in trying to capture this rapidly changing social reality—an unmaking of the known that remains indeterminate about the future—develops a singular aesthetics to transmit the sense of existential insecurity and instability. I will use Lynn Steger Strong’s novel *Want* as a case in point to argue that, in this novel, the foregrounding of precarity is achieved through a combination of formal and stylistic choices: a predominantly realist style interspersed with naturalistic sections, a circularity of plot that helps to convey the feeling of ‘being stuck’ for the newly-precarious, and a certain withholding of emotion in the representation, a ‘flat affect’ that nonetheless is meant to produce an affective response in readers. This, I suggest, is likewise becoming visible in other US literary fictions of the past decade.²³

Unhousing and the aesthetics of precarity

In one of the earliest engagements—2013—with the question of precarity in Anglo-American scholarship and literature, Jago Morrison defines the turn to precarity as ‘a changed sensibility in post-9/11 fiction’, one that is characterized by ‘a renewal of interest in the flow and foreclosure of affect, the resurgence of questions about vulnerability and our relationships to the other, and a heightened awareness of the social dynamics of seeing’.²⁴ Some years later,

Connell can already speak of a coherent body of works in which this turn to precarity has materialized, albeit in diverse ways. In ‘Anxious Reading’, he lays out the shape that such a precarity novel takes: a mode of ‘contemporary fiction, predominantly realist, that depicts vulnerable subjects in the grip of escalating crises resulting from an endemic uncertainty that is a condition of contemporary capitalism’.²⁵ Of particular importance is that the precarity novel does not present the character’s vulnerability in a teleological way, either as the result of one particular crisis (in the best sense of the term, as an inflection point) or trending towards a conflict and eventual resolution (whether positive or negative). Rather, ‘the crises in these novels are marked by a particular narrative dynamic in which the worsening of the character’s fate is never met by a culminating catastrophe. The characteristic form of such writing is a novel that presents a seemingly permanent condition of anticipation of unrealized crisis’.²⁶ Indeed, together with the feeling of anxiety—that has been identified among the dominant affects of twenty-first-century precarity, next to anomie and anger—one of the main characteristics of the precarity novel is its narrative circularity, its sense of stasis, something akin to what Berlant described as living in the ‘impasse’,²⁷ the feeling of being stuck in the permanent (endemic) crisis that is the present.

I also want to suggest that part of what contributes to this sense of stasis is the way characters and situations are represented, with a type of ‘flat affect’ which Berlant describes as an underperformance of emotion,²⁸ a muted response to an experience that is not necessarily commensurate with its intensity.²⁹ In other words, a certain refusal to offer the customary responses that register (or seem to register) experiences in the expected way—X happens, you do Y—, expectations that I also associate with a ‘neoliberal economy of emotions’ that are ‘increasingly understood as resources to develop and manage’.³⁰ Flat affect is, on the contrary, a withholding—not an absence—of emotion that upsets conventional generic performances, a response that allows for a certain ‘degree of protection’ that impedes these affects from being translated, (de)codified, and depleted ‘into established genres for interpreting the world’.³¹

As a result, the ‘unreadability’ of the emotions presented in the narrative, which can also be understood as a lack of coherence (between the crisis and the reaction to it) or disorientation, contributes to what Connell identifies as one of the key characteristics of the precarity novel: its capacity to elicit an ‘anxious reading’. Depending on the meanings that readers attach to these representations of vulnerability and dislocation, the experience of reading the precarity novel can elicit responses that go beyond recognizing oneself in the representation of anxiety and insecurity within the text—feeling empathy—and may translate

instead into actual feelings of unease, anxiety, or being stressed or unsettled.³² As Connell suggests, the anxious reading that the precarity novel can provoke ‘operates at the level of affect rather than, precisely, at the level of representation’, and it emanates from its very ordinariness and realism.³³ It is a type of recognition of the known that, I argue, does not foreclose its being uneasily unstated, withheld, and diffuse. Connell also considers what kinds of interpretative readings can emerge from this initial affective encounter, mostly because ‘political solidarity . . . is rarely depicted in the novels themselves’.³⁴ Indeed, any potential for action or collective mobilization would be projected outside of the text, from characters to readers—precisely because characters remain ‘stuck’, unable or unwilling to act—and readers could transform the anxiety experienced in the act of reading into ‘a mode of solidarity’.³⁵ For Connell, the affective power of the precarity novel lies precisely in its potential to elicit such a political response—again, barely represented in the text—, as it would in fact contribute to an awareness among the precarious of ‘being’ a class—understood here as a grouping of people that share a socioeconomic status—and this kind of subjective solidarity could be the basis for providing the precariat with a form of class-consciousness that many critics argue is lacking at the moment.

But precisely because social class cannot be neatly restricted to income and type of occupation—because it also includes differences in educational level, lifestyle, social status, and cultural capital, all of which constitute both an objective reality and a subjective lived experience—³⁶ it is so difficult for the precarious to think of themselves collectively in terms of class. Some would argue that this is the result of a successful neoliberal process of post-industrial atomization of the workplace—gig economies, increasing temporality, constant turnover, fragmented or non-existent workplaces. Others have engaged with the notion of ‘the cognitariat’ to describe a particular subset within the precariat: highly-educated workers who perform cognitive work (intellectuals, academics, tech workers, lawyers, doctors, artists, etc.) under the same conditions of contingency and insecurity as the working-class precarious but with an added dose of auto-exploitation, driven by the deceptive allure of ‘vocation’ and ‘flexibility’ and the impossibility of *really* quantifying their ‘productivity’ in material terms.³⁷ In short, the difficulty in rallying the precariat as a ‘class’ through traditional categories is what leads Berlant to think of it as an ‘affective class’, a collection of people that are bound together only by their *sensing* precarity, pointing to the ‘class incoherence’ at precisely the time when the extension of precarity has a ‘universalizing claim’.³⁸ So much so that Berlant even speaks of a ‘Precarity State’, one that has declared itself bankrupt and is unable to support its citizens, who are now too expensive to maintain, a characterization that resonates deeply with other

recent formulations of the neoliberal present such as ‘precarity capitalism’ (Azmanova), ‘rentier capitalism’ (Christophers), and even ‘neofeudalism’ (Dean, among others).³⁹ What all these notions have in common is that they draw attention to the State’s capitulation to the power of private financial capital, the dismantling of the structures of public assistance for the sake of profit, and the ensuing mass precarisation of working people into an underclass, a social structure that may well resemble the ‘mass serfdom’ of an extinct feudal order, according to Dean. In this context, the Precarity State acts as nothing more than ‘an emergency responder’,⁴⁰ and people get used to the embedding of the emergency, or the crisis, in the ordinary (and this is what Berlant means by ‘crisis ordinariness’), become inured to the depletion of expectations. Thus, the condition of ‘feeling precarious’, as Berlant describes it, has many valences, from ‘the condition of instability created by changes in the compact between capital and the state’, to an affective designation that serves to describe a historical present ‘increasingly not only without guarantees but without predictables’.⁴¹ Berlant even suggests that precarity could potentially serve an ideological function, as a rallying cry for political action. Indeed, one has to wonder whether the self-identification as the ‘basket of deplorables’ derided by Hillary Clinton in 2016 did not serve as one such rallying cry for Donald Trump’s win; the mutual reinforcements between socioeconomic precariousness and anti-establishment populisms (both on the left and right) have been well established by now. However, it is precisely this ideological and social heterogeneity that, in my view, figures as the main impediment to the possibility and probability of political solidarity and action from the newly-precarious: they are a ‘class’ that is held together only through the awareness of a precarity that is not always experienced as shared; in other words, bound together only by the affective dimension of their (increasingly individual or partisan) encounter with the contemporary.

Regardless of the political potential that aesthetic representations may have, we can see Berlant’s precise diagnosis of the newly-precarious as an affective class already replicated in a variety of artistic forms, and in this sense my analysis is indebted to the work of Taylor Nygaard and Jorie Lagerwey who, in their recent intervention *Horrible White People: Gender, Genre, and Television’s Precarious Whiteness* (2020), argue for a shift towards an aesthetics of precarity in British-American televisual fiction.⁴² The authors draw attention to the increasing number of productions that are built upon the exploration and centring of ‘White precarity’—understood as a ‘general lack of security and sense of threat’ (15) experienced by mostly ‘liberal middle-class White characters confronted with precarity for the first time’. The sense of precarity in many cases revolves around ‘the loss of easily accessible home ownership’ (21), which, as Nygaard and Lagerwey contend, reveals ‘the internalized assumption that those

homes were an unquestionable part of their class identity'.⁴³ Moreover, they link the emergence of this cycle centred on 'beleaguered, exhausted White people'—a hypervisibilisation or centring of Whiteness—in televisual media precisely 'at the same time as images of black and white children victimized by state violence spread across the news'.⁴⁴ In the authors' definition, these 'Horrible White People' are 'educated, urban-dwelling, White liberals, who are presumed to mobilize for civil rights and vote for left-leaning politicians, [but who] often react with an ineffectual fear that neither returns them to their former status and security nor leaves room to organize for those whom they claim to support' (38). In other words, these Horrible White People and their attendant 'ugly feelings', to borrow Sianne Ngai's formulation, are not only a symptom of but may also be part of the problem, and their cultural representation can perhaps be read as an escape valve for a larger, cultural malaise, Nygaard and Lagerwey argue.

Leaving aside the necessarily longer exploration of whether underlying racism and White supremacist attitudes—or simply, a sense of lost privilege—may be fuelling the emergence of a cultural category centred on White precarity—with the consequent effect of shoring up the hegemonic structures of White supremacy, which is one of Nygaard and Lagerwey's main contentions in their excellent intervention—, this is the kind of trend that I am arguing has begun to be visible in contemporary US literature. I suggest that Strong's novel *Want* is a good starting point to think about how a twenty-first-century US literature of precarity may be taking shape, about how it may be engaging with a present characterized by a pervasive sense of stasis and 'cruel pessimism' among the (former) middle classes. Strong's narrator is a familiar kind of character: young, White, privileged, with an Ivy-League education and no career prospects, mired in debt and 'one root canal away from missed rent and a forced move'.⁴⁵ Part of a generation raised under entrepreneurial, neoliberal creeds such as 'Do what you love and you'll never work a day in your life!', only to find that they are perennially tired, that three low-paying jobs are not enough to pay the rent, and that the hypothetical promise does not deliver. The novel is aptly—and deceptively—titled 'want', as it illustrates how the nature of this want has been transformed under 'the affective legacies of austerity, precarity, and neoliberalism'.⁴⁶ The fraying fantasies that Berlant had identified as 'upward mobility, job security, political and social equality, and lively, durable intimacy'⁴⁷ have all been cheapened into, for Strong's characters, nothing more and nothing less than the desire to be able to pay the rent the following month. As I have been arguing, housing insecurity is a central element of 'feeling precarious', not just in the material sense of shelter but because of how it reveals the receding associations between homeownership and middle-class status. As such, the novel aptly begins and ends with the narrator's reflections on her inadequate housing, and in trying

to apprehend this precariousness the narrative produces a very tangible affect, one that goes beyond mere recognition on the part of the reader and comes closer to discomfort, unease, or anguish, an affective interpellation that is one of the characteristics that Connell argues for in the literature of precarity: a very ‘anxious reading’.

Empty mansions, untenable mortgages: the US novels of the crisis

In order to illustrate how these aesthetic shifts materialize in Strong’s *Want* as a novel of precarity in a way that sets it apart from the corpus concerned with the financial crisis of 2007-2008 (and which I have been referring to as ‘novels of the crisis’), I will comment briefly on two early novels—Adam Haslett’s *Union Atlantic* and Jess Walter’s *The Financial Lives of the Poets*—that also feature housing as a structuring theme. While one might expect matters of housing to figure prominently in novels of the crisis—especially because of the gaping hole left by the housing bubble after it burst—, in many of these narratives there is only a spectral presence of the (soon-to-be foreclosed) homes or of the people affected,⁴⁸ and when houses do feature—as is the case here—they carry with them certain ideological investments that, I will argue, are not available to the newly-precarious a decade later.⁴⁹

In her review article ‘Fictional Capital’, Elizabeth Gumport argues that many of the novels that emerged out of the financial-mortgage crisis in the United States are concerned primarily with the fictitious nature of the capital traded by Wall Street—in the form of collateralized debt obligations and the myriad financial products that gamble on the performance of housing mortgages—, the mismanagement of which leads to the crash.⁵⁰ Similarly, Mirosław Miernik argues in *Rethinking Fiction after the 2007/8 Financial Crisis* that while some such novels do in fact ‘present such issues as poverty, wealth, equality, distinction, opportunity’, they do it mainly in relation ‘to traditional criticisms of consumer culture and the US economy, particularly those issues that have received more attention as a result of the crisis’.⁵¹ In other words, and as the language of Miernik’s study suggests, the corpus resonates with terms like ‘financial’, ‘consumer’, ‘economy’ and the like, and in doing so it reveals the particular slant—financial or economy-oriented—of many of these novels, which clearly distinguishes them from those concerned with the representation of precarity. This interest in the workings of high finance, macroeconomics, and the market in so many of these early examples of novels of the crisis translates into a focus on the system as system—indeed on the workings of neoliberalism as finance—rather than on the long-term and material aftershocks of the housing crisis and rising precarity on ordinary citizens. And even when the

focus does get closer to the individual—for example, in Walter’s *The Financial Lives*, as we will see below—the ‘system’ is never too far in the background.

The plot of Adam Haslett’s *Union Atlantic* (2010), often billed as a ‘prophetic’ novel of the crisis, is structured around the feud between two neighbours on account of their respective houses.⁵² Investment banker and ‘self-made man’ Doug Fanning has built himself a ‘casino of a house’ (15), a ‘Greek Revival château’ (25) ‘designed to draw attention’ (24); in other words, what we could cheekily call a McMansion. ‘This steroidal offense’ (25) stands right next to Charlotte Graves’ dilapidated house, the former vacation home of her childhood, which she spent in a wealthy town outside of Boston. Her house has ‘weathered shingles, a listing brick chimney, and a slight dip in the long rear slant of the roof. . . . [It was] one of those New England saltboxes that historical preservation societies kept tabs on, although not too closely by the looks of it’ (21). The source of the conflict is—besides the fact that it is an eyesore—that Doug’s house has been built on forest land that Charlotte’s family had donated to the town for its preservation. The narrative pays close attention to the interiors of both houses, which play a univocal role as extensions of their owners’ psychic state. A panic-inducing void is the dominant affect produced by Doug’s sparsely furnished and almost empty mansion: cold, impersonal, not really lived-in. The sheer amount of space between the bed and the wall produces morning panics for Doug, and details slowly emerge of his troubled childhood. Raised by an alcoholic, single mother in a dingy apartment on the other side of the town, where she cleans the houses of the rich, her perennial silence haunts Doug and is the source of a gaping emotional hole in his life. He is cold, calculating, detached, emotionally unavailable, and there is no character development as the story moves forward. His mansion is ‘a finished space marked by nothing. Without content or association. A perfect blank’ (75). On the other end of the feud, Charlotte is a retired history teacher with early signs of dementia, whose

circularities drew energy from the very decrepitude of [her] place. The house *was* her argument, its density of association imperative to preserve. It may have belonged to others once, to [her] ancestors or [her] parents, but it was all hers now, the physical form her opinion of the world had come to take. How could he ever change her mind while living inside of it like this? (167)

The ‘he’ that is speaking in this excerpt is Charlotte’s brother, who is also the Chair of the New York Federal Reserve Bank and is charged with dealing with the multibillion-dollar fraud committed by Doug’s investment bank (Union Atlantic) and, later, with Charlotte’s suicide, in

the process of which she burns her house down. Interestingly, the novel is set in the post-9/11 world of 2001-2002, although by all accounts the attention paid to the trading fraud and the financial mismanagement at Union Atlantic—a conglomerate that is ‘too big to fail’, common parlance in the 2007-2008 financial crash—and its possible repercussions on the global financial system are centre stage. We can easily read Charlotte’s demise—her decaying mind, the destruction of her house and all the memories it contained—as a stand-in for a receding world order (social, liberal democracy?) that has given way to the rule of global finance—an impersonal, ruthless, indifferent order that is perfectly represented by the void at the centre of Doug’s mansion, an emotional black hole.⁵³ While Doug’s desire to build and own a house—an obscene, monstrous house—is initially ascribed to the outsize profits that can be made (‘Before Doug ever opened the front door, the value of his new property had risen thirty percent’ [16]), the novel does invite a reading of it as, ultimately, a failed attempt at self-assurance, a desire to own and to ‘be’ who the house says you are, ‘what’ the house represents (in this case: a rich bully who made his way out of nothing). In short, this is not a novel concerned with the effects of the crisis on ordinary people and how they struggle to get by but with the lack of scruples and accountability and the corrupt workings of the financial system. The novel foregoes any texture and granularity that would be afforded by the representation of the lives of those on the receiving end of the crisis and offers a clinical and aseptic depiction of the lives of the ultra-rich (whether old money or new), in a prose that is crisp and clean, and that strikes the reader as purposefully unemotional (especially in the sections dealing with Doug).

A very different approach is taken in Jess Walter’s *The Financial Lives of Poets* (2009)—credited as the first US novel to address the aftermath of the 2008 financial crash—although the desire for homeownership similarly retains a powerful hold on its narrator.⁵⁴ Despite the ironic use of ‘financial’ in its title and unlike many of the subsequent US novels of the crisis, it is not concerned with the workings of high finance but with how the crisis (which he calls ‘another 7/11’, conflating the enormity of the event’s ripple effects with the mundane ubiquitousness of a grocery store) *indirectly* affects the narrator, an ordinary, middle-class man. He is a journalist who, just before the Wall Street crash, had decided to quit his job at a local newspaper to set up ‘an unlikely poetry-and-investment website’, only to get ‘buried in the housing collapse just as [his] senile father moved in’ (5). The father has lost his house after being scammed by a stripper—an image that seems a deliberate metaphor, in Walter’s tongue-in-cheek style, of the unethical dealings of Wall Street. However, this crisis in fact simply

figures as the tipping point that follows a number of earlier crises, in what the narrator refers to as ‘several other recent *setbacks*—missed payments, ensuing penalties, house refi’s,⁵⁵ debt consolidations, various family crises and my untimely job loss’ (4), the latter a result of the shrinking of the profession of journalism in the digital age (something about which Toby Miller has eloquently written in his piece ‘The Cognitariat’⁵⁶). What keeps the plot moving forward are the narrator’s efforts to not lose his recently-acquired and heavily mortgaged house to the bank (or to whatever financial entity has bought, unbeknownst to him, his mortgage debt), which unleashes a rather bizarre and comic set of events. The narrator befriends some low-level drug dealers at the 7/11 in his gentrified neighbourhood, figures that most of his middle-aged relations used to smoke marijuana in college and would love to get some now, and just as he devises a plan to sell enough to make up for his house payments, he is intercepted by the narcotics division of the FBI and is turned into an unwilling informant. As Gumport observes, even if the novel:

is weirdly effective because what it so blithely describes—people losing their jobs, people losing their homes, long-standing relationships fraying over money—is in fact happening all around us . . . the emotions stirred up are stirred up aimlessly, indeed a little cynically. Bad things occur but are never held to be the fault of bad decisions made by particular human beings.⁵⁷

It is quite telling that Gumport objects specifically to the lack of accountability in the novel, to things *just happening* to people, to people having the best intentions but messing up: precisely because some explanations and accountability need to be had for the dire (collective and individual) financial situation (at least in the critic’s mind). While Gumport is right about the emotional aimlessness of the narrative in general, I suggest that it does offer some rare moments of reflection: In particular, when the narrator questions his relation to his own house, ponders over the idea of homeownership, the ravages of gentrification—caused by people like himself—, the recklessness of the financial commitment of his mortgage, and the toll it takes on personal relations. The house is, as the narrator eventually admits, just a ‘dream of solvency’, a fantasy that, he feels, they should just let go and ‘float away into the sky . . . let someone else live in the big house’ (99). He admits to being bitterly disappointed:

not that my own home has lost half its value. What disappoints me is me—that I fell for their propaganda when *I knew better*, that I actually allowed myself to believe that a person could own a piece of the world when the truth is that anything you try to own ends up owning you. We're all just renting. (98).

'Rent', however, does not have the ominous connotations that I will later point out in Strong's novel; here it figures simply as a reflection on materialism and how we may end up being owned by the things we own—a meditation that is not really available to the urban precariat. Other than his thoughts on homeownership, and in fairness to Gumport's point, the narrator rarely seems to assume any responsibility for his own undoing, although the humorous tone of the narrative voice and the ludicrous plot twists seem to undermine this lack of accountability. The novel does offer, too, a scathing critique of the financial system—albeit in a short, four-page chapter—in which the narrator rebukes the media narratives that blame the crisis on 'poor people being allowed to borrow one hundred percent of inflated home prices' (134). However, as in the passage above, the narrative draws attention once again to the dream of homeownership being just that, an illusion, and the narrator-poet brings up Emily Dickinson—'*One need not be a chamber to be haunted, / One need not be a house*' (99)—lamenting that poets should keep reminding us that 'real estate' is best balanced 'with ethereal states' (98-99). In one key passage, the narrator reflects on a possible alternative that he, together with his wife and children, could take:

Who cares if we lose the fucking house next week? This house isn't us. We are us. *One need not be a house*. . . . So what . . . we default? Declare bankruptcy? Big deal. It doesn't matter where we go, what we do. Hell, I'll wash dishes, tend bar. You can clean houses. We can take the kids out of school, walk away from this big house, drift. Go from town to town, see the world, work menial jobs. Live. (99-100)

In other words, the house is a stand-in for middle-class status, 'a dream of solvency', but it is precisely the romanticization of the freedom that would be afforded by not owning a house that grounds the novel so firmly in its moment, corpus, and social milieu: If this were a novel dealing with precarity, as I have defined it in previous sections, the narrator would hardly need reminding that drifting, housing insecurity, and 'menial jobs' like washing dishes, bar tending,

and cleaning houses would provide nowhere near enough income to do what he so desires to do: 'Live'.

Generation Rent: Lynn Steger Strong's *Want*

Considerations about employment and housing are similarly at the forefront of Strong's *Want*, but the affective investment in homeownership that is on display in both Walter's and Haslett's novels is not available at all. Homeownership is not an option for the female narrator—it is not even an afterthought, is not mentioned at all—and tenancy is hanging in the balance. This, as Mike Savage argues in *Social Class in the 21st Century*, is perhaps the key economic division of our times because of the centrality of housing property as a source of wealth. On one side of the scale, those who have access to homeownership (and for some, even surplus housing from which to derive rents); on the other, the precariat, who is usually reliant on rented housing, which further contributes to their insecurity, as they are increasingly vulnerable to 'the will of another',⁵⁸ that is to say, the landlord, changing regulations, and the housing market. As Berlant reminds us, housing and precarity are intimately connected because 'at root, precarity is a condition of dependency—as a legal term, *precarious* describes the situation wherein your tenancy on your land is in someone else's hands'.⁵⁹

Strong's novel opens with a stark depiction of the narrator's living conditions in New York City in 2017, where she lives in a small, rented apartment with a husband and two daughters which can hardly be described as 'decent housing':

My alarm goes off at 4.30 every weekday morning, and I keep my phone lodged between the slatted stairs that lead up to the lofted bed my husband built us in a closet we use as a bedroom, so that I'm not able to press Snooze. I climb down in the dark and find the phone, which has often fallen. I turn off the alarm and put on my bra and tights and shirt and shoes and gloves and headband, grab my keys and phone, and lock the door behind me; I run miles and miles before anyone wakes up.⁶⁰

Intimacy has no room in this minute space and so it takes place in the bathroom shower, which is described as cold and with grimy tiles; what the novel achieves in these opening sections is to hit the reader with a sort of 'precarious realism',⁶¹ a naturalistic description of living conditions that are actually quite depressing. The narrator then goes on to describe a typical

working day and her long, daily commute on public trains that do not run well, in a tone that remains mostly emotionless, uncommitted, perhaps even *tired*. ‘On Twitter, the world is ending. A nuclear war is threatening, ice caps are melting, kids at school are shooting other kids at school’ (8), but nothing of the world outside intrudes in the retelling of the daily grind. The narrator is the daughter of two successful lawyers who, she is quick to point out, ‘came from nothing’ and made a fortune working hard (72). Therefore, she laments, ‘they thought anyone who was not also successful was not successful because they did not work hard enough’ (72)—that deeply entrenched mythology of the American Dream that also explains so much antagonism towards poverty as its main refutation. A generational rift is also revealed in the misinterpretation her parents—children of an earlier social contract for whom precarious existence seems to be a matter of choice—and this is a point that the novel insistently makes: the fact that her parents judge her by standards and expectations that no longer apply.⁶² She is part of the precarious cognitariat, with a PhD in Literature from Princeton and a soul-crushing job at a charter school⁶³—where she is constantly bombarded with inane managerial slogans like ‘*Looking forward to a joyfully driven professional day!*’ (8), Google spreadsheets, digital calendars, and attendance trackers—and a second teaching job as an adjunct at the University of Columbia, giving class late on Thursday evenings. Her husband works as a carpenter for rich clients on the weekends, so that they do not have to pay for childcare they cannot afford (103). A decade earlier he had obtained a ‘fancy degree’ (202) and a job at Lehman Brothers, before its collapse in 2008, which ‘freed’ him to pursue a career doing manual labour (which in hindsight is justified as what he has wanted to do all along, although the narrator is not very specific about this). The financial crisis is never presented as the root cause of this family’s precarious situation; rather, it is the audacity of wanting to live in New York City and of refusing to give up the hope that, one day, they may have jobs they like. In fact, the hope has become a continually deflating expectation that one day they may escape the ‘in-betweenness’ of their social position: having made huge investments in an education to ‘succeed’—and the social relations that go with it—yet barely hanging on. In this, the novel stages the uneasy coexistence between optimism and pessimism, the fact that they are still hanging on to a ‘dream of solvency’ that is refuted by the narrative again and again.

There is no letup in Strong’s novel, as the narrator retells the daily indignities she faces (and commits) as they struggle to get by. She flouts the rules at school because she knows she will not be fired, because she has ‘the right look’ (i.e.: she is a White teacher in a school that caters to mostly Black and Hispanic students), she constantly lies about family emergencies in

order to get out of work early and spend her time reading novels in a nearby café, she disdains her younger White colleagues whom she finds insecure and unassertive, and she even considers an offer from a rich couple who want to buy her husband's sperm because he is good-looking. In other words, even reproduction is up 'for rent' in a world in which the precarious are exploited not just for their labour but as a source of raw material themselves.⁶⁴ Early on in the novel, the couple has to file for bankruptcy—not caused by a mortgage they cannot afford, but simply by the fact that they cannot make ends meet—and the narrator curtly recounts how they are not even able to do so until 'we finally had the two thousand dollars cash we had to pay [the lawyer] to declare officially that we had no money' (45). As they leave the courtroom, the narrator asks her husband: '*What is this supposed to feel like? . . . Relief?*' (45). But there is no relief, nor any other positive emotion that is able give the protagonists or the reader any reprieve. In these first sections the narrator constantly notes how colleagues and people around her seem 'anxious', 'scared', 'panic[ked]', 'desperate' (11) 'antsy', or 'uncomfortable' (13), someone even writes the word 'stasis' in block letters on the board in the classroom (83), but the narrative tone remains quite detached, even humorous. She admits her dissatisfaction at her own performance as a teacher, which she says is because 'I'm inconsistent, get distracted' (13)—sometimes she is so tired that not even her clandestine novel-reading can hold her attention—but, overall, the narrator seems to have calmly accepted a state of affairs that her 'scared' and 'antsy' fellow White colleagues have not.

As the story progresses, the narrator faces a number of 'crises'—again, situations that require her intervention, but none that seem like a turning point in the life trajectory she is describing—although in some instances we intuit that the emotional flatness of the narrative voice may soon begin to crack. In fact, the structure of the novel along two timelines—one in 2017, when the narrative takes place, and the other offering flashbacks to the narrator's teenage and college years—actually serves to underscore the emotional underperformance of the present. The flashback sections recall the origins of her difficult relationship with her parents and her estrangement from her best friend, and both stories are eventually updated in the 2017 timeline; in fact, it is only in relation to her parents and her friend that some—incredibly modest—progress can be said to have taken place at the end. Other than that, the novel exudes a sense of stagnation and inevitability that is also replicated in formal terms, in that it concludes in the same way that it begins, with the narrator reflecting on the inadequacy of their living arrangements as they are forced to move, once again. The apartment is not the same but it could be, as it is all that the couple can afford in the increasingly speculative and gentrifying

environment of New York City. And this is a key consideration when thinking about the centrality of housing for the literature of precarity: the impact of gentrification on the price of property and rents in the inner city and how people are continuously displaced to the outskirts.

In the introduction to *The Gentrification Plot. New York and the Postindustrial Crime Novel* (2022), Thomas Heise poses a question that is simple in its premise but momentous in its implications, particularly for a genre that is traditionally strongly intertwined with the urban landscape, such as the crime novel: If the city is the site where the novel takes place and the crimes committed in the city are its events, what happens when the city, and the crimes happening there, are radically altered by gentrification? For Heise, the result is a new development in the genre, ‘the gentrification plot’, which stages ‘conflicts over territory and real estate’.⁶⁵ While it may be too bold for me to suggest anything remotely similar in the novel of precarity, gentrification is often featured as the source of the lack of affordable and adequate housing in these narratives, and I want to insist on the centrality of housing insecurity to the ‘feeling precarious’, as is the case in Strong’s novel. Heise’s tracing of the transformations of New York City through the mayoral terms of Rudy Giuliani (1994-2001) and Michael Bloomberg (2002-2013) shows how the groundwork was laid for today’s housing crisis by turning New York into a luxury product.⁶⁶ If precarisation is the desiccation of the public structures of assistance resulting from the state’s capitulation to private capital, the gentrification of New York City under Mayor Bloomberg—prioritizing the construction of office space and the upscaling of residential areas to attract corporate capital—is ‘its apotheosis, subjecting the very urbanism of the city itself to [...] corporate logic’.⁶⁷ As Heise notes, the bullish narrative of this post-1990s New York—crime-free and opulent—has been retold indirectly in countless TV series, from *Seinfeld* to *Sex and the City*, where the absence of crime is the ‘precondition for plotlines about the anodyne and amusing foibles of bourgeois life’⁶⁸ and stories about the personal and professional fulfilment of the middle-classes. This, as I have noted earlier in reference to Nygaard and Lagerwey’s *Horrible White People*, may already be starting to change through the centring of White precarity, which among its many uncertainties includes a diminishing ‘right to the city’⁶⁹ that results in exorbitant rents and profit-driven displacement to the outer boroughs.

As I have already mentioned, this is how Strong’s novel ends, with a forced move further out in Brooklyn after the couple gets notice from the owners of the building that their apartment block is being converted to privately-owned condos. As tenants, they have ‘the option to purchase [their] apartment or to leave’ (198) but, of course, that ‘option’ is never really there, as they do not have the money to buy property—least of all in New York. They

consider leaving the city altogether; they even joke about joining a commune upstate or moving in with the husband's parents, who live in 'a one-bedroom house so far north in Maine that they're often snowed in for weeks or months' (201). As they weigh up their non-options, the novel delivers what is one of the most telling depictions of their precarious state and, also, of how precarity is unevenly distributed, because at least they have '*rich parents to call*' (201). Some of their neighbours are moving with their children upstate, others are 'going to elder-care facilities that horrify them', while '[t]he gentrifiers, the people in the building who look most like us, mostly are either buying in or finding apartments south of the park' (202). Note how the gentrifiers 'look most like us' but they are not 'us', who are somewhere in-between and rapidly falling further away from the social class they perceive as their own. As they continue to consider what to do ('*I could call some of the old Lehman guys*'), the narrator finally asks her husband: '*What do you want, though?*' (202). The answer is devastating in its simplicity: '*To pay our rent, he says. To take care of our kids*' (202). Two very simple demands that can barely be fulfilled with the narrator's two 'adjunct jobs, a part-time freelance gig transcribing subtitles' and a prospective shift at a wine bar (203). Eventually, they are bailed out by her parents and move out to what she describes as 'a one-bedroom apartment farther down in Brooklyn in which my husband built us another loft bed in the room off of the kitchen and our girls sleep in bunk beds that we found on Craigslist even though they're too young' (204).

I proposed at the beginning of this article to think of unhousing not just as physical displacement but also as affective divestment, a sort of pessimistic depletion of expectations that, nonetheless, is on the brink of 'what feels virtually (im)possible'. When the narrator's mother asks her what she plans for the future and demands to know: '*At what point . . . is it time to cut your losses? At what point is it time to give up on this whole dream thing?*', the narrator is hit with the full recognition of their misunderstanding: '*What dream?*' (203). There are no dreams, only modest wants. Paying rent. Taking care of your kids. The novel, as already stated, ends very much the way it started, in a circularity that points to the unavailability of any optimistic outlook for the future, and readers are not encouraged to imagine that conditions will improve. As Berlant wrote: '[A]ll attachment is optimistic';⁷⁰ what I have tried to illustrate in this essay is how reading the novel of precarity as a process of unhousing—as displacement and divestment—allows us to grasp how, in the mutually-constitutive relationship and competition between the affective structures of sentimental optimism and cruel pessimism, the literature of precarity clearly seems to be trending towards the latter. Whether that is enough to rally the precarious to a shared political conscience and solidarity remains to be seen.

¹ Lauren Berlant, *Cruel Optimism* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2011).

² Nancy Fraser, *Cannibal Capitalism. How Our System Is Devouring Democracy, Care, and the Planet—and What We Can Do about It* (New York and London: Verso, 2022).

³ Dia Da Costa, ‘Cruel Pessimism and Waiting for Belonging: Towards a Global Political Economy of Affect’, *Cultural Studies* 30, no.1 (2016): 1-23. Da Costa’s formulation of cruel pessimism emerges from her analysis of a project of activist theater in India by a tribe who were designated ‘born criminals’ under British colonial law and are still treated as such. She offers the notion of cruel pessimism as an affective response to conditions of marginality and/or (neo)colonial subjugation, arguing that in this context of having to negotiate with their own branded criminality, there are two ‘competing affective structures: sentimental optimism and cruel pessimism’ (3). These are in a mutually constitutive relation because if pessimism is what feels (im)possible, sentimental optimism is, as Berlant notes, that ‘scene of negotiated sustenance that makes life bearable’ (Berlant, *Cruel Optimism*, 14). Robyn Wiegman, ‘Cruel Pessimisms’, Keynote Address at The Futures of American Studies Institute, Dartmouth College, delivered on 24 June 2022.

⁴ Da Costa, ‘Cruel Pessimism’, 6.

⁵ Berlant, *Cruel Optimism*, 14.

⁶ For the mutually reinforcing relation between socioeconomic precarity and right-wing populism, see Paul Apostolidis, ‘Desperate Responsibility: Precarity and Right-Wing Populism’, *Political Theory* 50, no.1 (2022): 114-141.

⁷ Liam Connell, *Precarious Labour and the Contemporary Novel* (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017), 57-89; and ‘Anxious Reading. The Precarity Novel and the Affective Class’, in *Precarity in Contemporary Literature and Culture*, ed. Emily J. Hogg and Peter Simonsen (London: Bloomsbury, 2021).

⁸ I will use the term ‘novels of the crisis’ for the sake of clarity. Scholars like Daniel Mattingly have called these novels ‘crash fictions’, while Arne De Boever has offered the term ‘finance fictions’, although none of these terms seems to have gained much traction in US scholarship. See Daniel Mattingly, ‘“Crash Fiction”: American Literary Novels of the Global Financial Crisis’, in *The Great Recession in Fiction, Film, and Television*, ed. Kirk Boyle and Daniel Mrozowski (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2013); and Arne De Boever, *Finance Fictions. Realism and Psychosis in a Time of Economic Crisis* (New York: Fordham University Press, 2018). In contrast, ‘crash fictions’ is current in discussions of contemporary Irish literature, where scholars commonly refer to ‘postcrash / post-crash’ Irish fiction. See for example, Justine Jordan, ‘A New Irish Literary Boom: The Post-Crash Stars of Fiction’, *The Guardian*, 16 October 2015; Annie Galvin, ‘Post-crash Fiction and the Aesthetics of Austerity in Kevin Barry’s *City of Bohane*’, *Critique: Studies in Contemporary Fiction* 59, no. 5 (2018): 578-595; Adam Kelly, ‘Ireland’s Real Economy: Postcrash Fictions of the Celtic Tiger’, in *The New Irish Studies. Twenty-First-Century Critical Revisions*, ed. Paige Reynolds (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020), 195-210; and Mary M. McGlynn, *Broken Irelands: Literary Form in Post-Crash Irish Fiction* (Syracuse: Syracuse University Press, 2022).

⁹ Connell, 'Anxious Reading', 27.

¹⁰ For Berlant's formulation of the 'technologies of patience', see *The Queen of America Goes to Washington City. Essays on Sex and Citizenship* (Durham: Duke University Press, 1997), 222. For a sustained analysis of their formulation of flat affect, see Robbie Duschinsky and Emma Wilson, 'Flat Affect, Joyful Politics and Enthralled Attachments: Engaging with the Work of Lauren Berlant', *International Journal of Politics, Culture, and Society* 28 (2014): 179-190.

¹¹ It is beyond the scope of this chapter to parse the histories and broad range of theoretical uses of the related terms 'precarity', 'precariousness', and 'precarisation', but of those studies that have done so, I have found the following especially useful: Jasbir Puar, 'Precarity Talk: A Virtual Roundtable with Lauren Berlant, Judith Butler, Bojana Cvejić, Isabell Lorey, Jasbir Puar, and Ana Vujanović' *TDR* 56, no. 4 (2012): 163–77; Isabell Lorey, *State of Insecurity: Government of the Precarious* (London and New York: Verso, 2015); Sieglinde Lemke, *Inequality, Poverty and Precarity in Contemporary American Culture* (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016); Jennifer Lawn, 'Precarity: A Short Literary History, from Colonial Slum to Cosmopolitan Precariat', *Interventions* 19, no. 7 (2017): 1026-1040; Emily J. Hogg, 'Introduction', in *Precarity in Contemporary Literature and Culture*, ed. Emily J. Hogg and Peter Simonsen (London: Bloomsbury, 2021); Barbara Schmidt-Haberkamp and Marion Gymnich, 'An Introduction', in *Representing Poverty and Precarity in a Postcolonial World*, ed. Barbara Schmidt-Haberkamp, Marion Gymnich and Klaus P. Schneider (Leiden: Brill, 2022); and the aforementioned Liam Connell (2017; 2021).

¹² Connell, *Precarious Labour*; and 'Anxious Reading'.

¹³ Guy Standing, *The Precariat: The New Dangerous Class* (London: Bloomsbury, 2011).

¹⁴ Maribel Casas-Cortés, 'Precarious Writings: Reckoning the Absences and Reclaiming the Legacies in the Current Poetics/Politics of Precarity', *Current Anthropology* 62, no. 5 (2021): 510.

¹⁵ Judith Butler, *Precarious Lives: The Powers of Mourning and Violence* (London and New York: Verso, 2004); and *Frames of War; When Is Life Grievable?* (London and New York: Verso, 2009).

¹⁶ Pierre Bourdieu, *Acts of Resistance: Against the New Myths of Our Time* (Cambridge: Polity, 1998); Guy Standing, *The Precariat: The New Dangerous Class* (London: Bloomsbury, 2011); Ben Anderson, *Encountering Affect. Capacities, Apparatuses, Conditions* (London: Routledge, 2014); Javier López Alós, *Crítica de la razón precaria. La vida intelectual ante la obligación de lo extraordinario* (Madrid: Los Libros de la Catarata, 2019); Judith Butler, *Precarious Life. The Powers of Mourning and Violence* (New York and London: Verso, 2004) and *Frames of War. When Is Life Grievable?* (New York and London: Verso, 2009); and Isabell Lorey, *State of Insecurity: Government of the Precarious* (New York and London: Verso, 2015).

¹⁷ Joseph B. Entin, *Living Labor. Fiction, Film, and Precarious Work* (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 2023), 122.

¹⁸ Emily J. Hogg, 'Introduction', in *Precarity in Contemporary Literature and Culture*, ed. Emily J. Hogg and Peter Simonsen (London: Bloomsbury, 2021), 1. It is precisely this 'newfound' quality of encroaching precarity in affluent Western countries that leads me to centre my analysis on Euro-American scholarship and fiction, rather than on the also

excellent work being produced in, for example, South America. While the experience of precariousness and ‘crisis ordinariness’ is certainly not foreign to the region, there are qualitative nuances that demand a knowledgeable approach to its varied histories and social contexts, which are beyond the scope of this article.

¹⁹ As she points out, ‘precarity’ entered the *Collins Dictionary* in 2017 and the *Oxford English Dictionary* in 2018. Albenaz Azmanova, ‘Precarity for All’, *Post-Neoliberalism. Pathways for Transformative Economics and Politics*, 29 November 2023, <https://www.postneoliberalism.org/articles/precarity-for-all/>.

²⁰ Lauren Berlant, ‘Austerity, Precarity, Awkwardness’, *Supervalent Thought*, November 2011, <https://supervalentthought.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2011/12/berlant-aaa-2011final.pdf>.

²¹ In Spain, for example, precarity novels have been grouped as ‘novelas de la crisis’ because they emerged out of the 2008-2010 economic crisis in Europe, but this label has been challenged by Pablo Valdivia precisely because they perform a sustained exploration of the precarity and vulnerability of the subject. He proposes instead the category of ‘literatura desheredada’ (disinherited literature). A similar focus is used by Emily Horton in her study on British ‘crisis fictions’, where she underscores the centrality of the feeling of anxiety, which brings them closer to Connell’s definition of the precarity novel. See Pablo Valdivia, ‘Narrando la crisis financiera de 2008 y sus repercusiones’, *452°F. Revista de teoría de la literatura y literatura comparada* 15 (2016): 18-36; and Emily Horton, *Contemporary Crisis Fictions: Affect and Ethics in the Modern British Novel* (Basingstoke and New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2014).

²² For US cinema of precarity, see Lauren Berlant, *Cruel Optimism* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2011), 161-263; Katarzyna Paszkiewicz, “‘Tipped over, but still growing’”: Cruel Optimism and Queer Temporalities in *The Florida Project*”, *Quarterly Review of Film and Video* 39, no.1 (2022): 139-169; and Joseph B. Entin, *Living Labor. Fiction, Film, and Precarious Work* (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 2023). For televisual media, see Taylor Nygaard and Jorie Lagerwey, *Horrible White People. Gender, Genre, and Television’s Precarious Whiteness* (New York: New York University Press, 2020). For US culture at large, see Sieglinde Lemke, *Inequality, Poverty and Precarity in Contemporary American Culture* (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016). For US drama, see Ana Fernández-Caparrós, ‘Intimations of Precarity in Twenty-First-Century U.S. Drama: Faltering Voices of the Precariat in Annie Baker’s *The Flick*’, *Cultura, lenguaje y representación* 25 (2021): 119-133 and ‘Confronting the Labor-Market and Housing Crises in Post-Recession U.S. Drama: Lisa D’Amour’s *Detroit* and Stephen Karam’s *The Humans*’, *Alicante Journal of English Studies* 43 (2025): 81-99.

²³ For the purposes of this article, my analysis is restricted to novels dealing with a newfound sense of precarity and its relation to housing; in this respect, Vikki Warner’s *Tenemental. Adventures of a Reluctant Landlady* (New York: Feminist Press, 2018) is an interesting case in point. However, as its title suggests, the narrator is not a tenant but a precarious landlady, which probably deserves an article of its own. I want to credit and thank Carolin M. Jesussek at the Obama Institute in Mainz for bringing Warner’s novel to my attention.

²⁴ Jago Morrison, ‘The Turn to Precarity in Twenty-First Century Fiction’, *American, British and Canadian Studies Journal* 21 (2013): 10. Not to belabor the point, but Morrison’s article serves as a perfect illustration of my earlier claim: While the theoretical argument draws

heavily from U.S. scholarship, the close reading of the literary texts is devoted exclusively to British fiction (Trezza Azzopardi's novel *Remember Me* and recent work by Zadie Smith).

²⁵ Connell, 'Anxious Reading', 28.

²⁶ Connell, 'Anxious Reading', 28. For a more sustained analysis, see Liam Connell, *Precarious Labour*, 57-89.

²⁷ Berlant, *Cruel Optimism*, 191-222.

²⁸ Lauren Berlant, 'Structures of Unfeeling: Mysterious Skin', *International Journal of Politics, Culture, and Society* 28 (2015): 193. In their thinking about flat affect, Berlant draws from its use in psychiatric discourse, where 'flat' designates an 'expressionless presentation', 'a kind of emotional opacity' in which affective display is of little range and intensity, and where the person has no clear idea of 'what the feelings they experience mean or what bearing they may have'. See Robbie Duschinsky and Emma Wilson, 'Flat Affect, Joyful Politics and Enthralled Attachments: Engaging with the Work of Lauren Berlant', *International Journal of Politics, Culture, and Society* 28 (2014): 185.

²⁹ Duschinsky and Wilson, 'Flat Affect', 185.

³⁰ Rachel Greenwald Smith, *Affect and American Literature in the Age of Neoliberalism* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 6.

³¹ Duschinsky and Wilson, 'Flat Affect', 187.

³² Connell, 'Anxious Reading', 35.

³³ Connell, 'Anxious Reading', 39, 34.

³⁴ Connell, 'Anxious Reading', 34.

³⁵ Connell, 'Anxious Reading', 36.

³⁶ Dave Hill and Alpesh Maisuria, 'Social Class', in *Encyclopaedia of Marxism and Education*, ed. Alpesh Maisuria (Leiden: Brill, 2022), 624-643.

³⁷ The term 'cognitariat' was originally coined by techno-futurist Alvin Toffler in 1983 to refer to the rise of knowledge workers in a post-industrial world driven by AI systems; it was later repurposed on the left by critics like Franco 'Bifo' Berardi, Antonio Negri, and Toby Miller. See Alvin Toffler, *Previews and Premises* (New York: William Morrow, 1983); Franco Berardi, 'What does Cognitariat Mean? Work, Desire and Depression', *Cultural Studies Review* 11, no. 2 (September 2005): 57-63; Antonio Negri, *Goodbye Mister Socialism* (Paris: Seuil, 2007); and Toby Miller and Pal Ahluwalia, 'The Cognitariat', *Social Identities* 18, no.3 (2012): 259-260.

³⁸ Berlant, 'Austerity, Precarity, Awkwardness', 2.

³⁹ See Albenaz Azmanova, *Capitalism on Edge: How Fighting Precarity Can Achieve Radical Change without Crisis or Utopia* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2020); Brett Christophers, *Rentier Capitalism. Who Owns the Economy, and Who Pays for It?* (London and New York: Verso, 2020); and Jodi Dean, 'Neofeudalism: The End of Capitalism?', *Los Angeles Review of Books*, 12 May 2020, <https://lareviewofbooks.org/article/neofeudalism-the-end-of-capitalism/>. In the latter, Dean provides a clear-eyed analysis of how the neofeudal hypothesis is deployed both on the right and on the left, with opposing ideological

foundations and outcomes, and how it could be mobilized by the left to examine ‘both the appeal and the weaknesses of popular left ideas’.

⁴⁰ Berlant, ‘Austerity, Precarity, Awkwardness’, 3.

⁴¹ Berlant, ‘Austerity, Precarity, Awkwardness’, 2.

⁴² Taylor Nygaard and Jorie Lagerwey, *Horrible White People. Gender, Genre, and Television’s Precarious Whiteness* (New York: New York University Press, 2020).

⁴³ Nygaard and Lagerwey, *Horrible White People*, 21.

⁴⁴ Nygaard and Lagerwey, *Horrible White People*, 24.

⁴⁵ Hillary Kelly, ‘Want Is the Summer Book I Couldn’t Put Down’, *Vulture*, 22 May 2020, <https://www.vulture.com/2020/05/want-lynn-steger-strong-summer-book-i-couldnt-put-down.html>.

⁴⁶ Judith Butler, “‘What Would It Mean to Think That Thought?’: The Era of Lauren Berlant”, *The Nation*, 8 July 2021, <https://www.thenation.com/article/culture/lauren-berlant-obituary/>.

⁴⁷ Berlant, *Cruel Optimism*, 3.

⁴⁸ It is estimated that approximately 3.8 million homes were foreclosed nationwide in the period 2007-2010, bringing the number up to 7.8 million foreclosures for the period 2007-2016. See Sharada Dharmasankar and Bhash Mazumder, ‘Have Borrowers Recovered from Foreclosures during the Great Recession?’, *Chicago Fed Letter* No. 370 (2016), <https://www.chicagofed.org/publications/chicago-fed-letter/2016/370>.

⁴⁹ Paul Auster’s *Sunset Park* (2010) deserves a special mention here, as some would consider it a ‘novel of the crisis’ insofar as it offers powerful images of the foreclosing of houses after 2008 and the spectral presence of the residents who have been forced to abandon them, while its main plot takes place in a squat in Brooklyn. It is also interesting that some of its characters, formerly privileged or middle-class, are beginning to sense precarity as if for the first time; the Occupy movement is in the background and the squatters even attempt to create some alternative communal life. However, in typical Auster fashion, the realist impulse is met with layers of meta-fictional concerns to the point that it can hardly be defined as a precarity novel in the terms laid out by Connell.

⁵⁰ Elizabeth Gumpert, ‘Fictional Capital’, *n+1*, issue 10 (2010), <https://www.nplusonemag.com/issue-10/reviews/fictional-capital/>. Michael Lewis’s non-fiction chronicle *The Big Short: Inside the Doomsday Machine* (New York: W. W. Norton & Co., 2010), offers a very clarifying autopsy of how financial mismanagement in Wall Street led to the 2007-2008 crash; it was then adapted to film by director Adam McKay in 2015. Another very illuminating depiction of the nature of this crisis (and of the cold-heartedness and impersonality of ‘the system’) is the film *Margin Call* (2011, dir. J.C. Chandor).

⁵¹ Mirosław Aleksander Miernik, *Rethinking Fiction after the 2007/8 Financial Crisis. Consumption, Economics, and the American Dream* (London and New York: Routledge, 2021), n.p.

⁵² Adam Haslett, *Union Atlantic* (London: Atlantic Books, 2010). All subsequent citations from this source are included parenthetically in the text. All italics used are present in the original text.

⁵³ Haslett noted in an interview that, in his view, Charlotte's decaying mind is the decay of 'the liberal conscience. The postwar American, left-of-center liberalism that I think has been routed since Reagan' (Haslett qtd. in Amity Gaige, 'Interview with Adam Haslett', *The Literary Review. An International Journal of Contemporary Writing* 53, no.2, [2010], n.p.).

⁵⁴ Jess Walter, *The Financial Lives of the Poets* (London: Penguin, 2009). All subsequent citations from this source are included parenthetically in the text. All italics used are present in the original text.

⁵⁵ i.e. refinancing (of the mortgage debt).

⁵⁶ Miller, 'The Cognitariat', 2013.

⁵⁷ Gumpport, 'Fictional Capital', 2010.

⁵⁸ Connell, 'Anxious Reading', 27.

⁵⁹ Berlant, *Cruel Optimism*, 192. Italics in the original.

⁶⁰ Lynn Steger Strong, *Want* (New York: Henry Holt and Company, 2020), 7. All subsequent citations from this source are included parenthetically in the text. All italics used are present in the original text.

⁶¹ I am indebted to Michael Jonik for suggesting this. In one of the few studies I have found describing 'precarious realism' in narrative, Joseph B. Entin defines it as 'a constellation of novels and films that self-consciously deploy aesthetic techniques of realist representation to render the intimate and interpersonal, as well as the structural and material, dynamics and dimensions of economic, social, and epistemological precarity for working and nonworking poor people under emergent conditions of post-Fordist, global production and empire' (*Living Labor*, 9).

⁶² As Connell suggests, 'this contrast between generations is typical of the precarity novel' ('Anxious Reading', 38).

⁶³ Charter schools are neither public nor private schools because they receive public funding but operate independently from a state's school system. They are run by management organizations that are typically non-profit, although they are increasingly becoming for profit.

⁶⁴ A similar argument is made by Shoshana Zuboff in *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism. The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power* (New York: Public Affairs, 2019), where she argues that we have transitioned from customers/consumers of digital and social media to being the sources from which raw data is extracted.

⁶⁵ Thomas Heise, *The Gentrification Plot. New York and the Postindustrial Crime Novel* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2022), 6.

⁶⁶ For a great overview of New York City's housing crisis, see Michael Greenberg, 'Tenants Under Siege: Inside New York City's Housing Crisis', *The New York Review of Books*, 17 August 2017.

⁶⁷ Julian Brash qtd. in Heise, *The Gentrification Plot*, 3.

⁶⁸ Heise, *The Gentrification Plot*, 6.

⁶⁹ David Harvey, 'The Right to the City', *New Left Review* 53 (Sept/Oct 2008).

⁷⁰ Berlant, *Cruel Optimism*, 1.